

doi:10.5281/zenodo.16504034

Enzymes Assessment In The Liver Of *Clarias Gariepinus* Induced With Sublethal Concentrations Of Produced Water (PW)

Uwoubeingha, Ebibibo Edric Felix¹ & Inyang, Iniobong Reuben²

^{1,2}Department of Biological Sciences,
Niger Delta University, Amassoma Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Corresponding Email: patedmund34@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This research investigated the toxicological effects of produced water on *Clarias gariepinus* by assessing alterations in serum enzymes, after 30 days of exposure to graded concentrations of produced water, following standard experimental procedures. On termination of the experiment, a small portion of Liver from experimental fishes were collected by dissection, crushed in a ceramic mortar and harmonized with physiological saline. The mixture was then centrifuged for 15 minutes at 3000 rpm. Thereafter, the supernatants were collected in sample bottles for enzymes assay. The results reveals that AST values in the liver spiked from 54.33 ± 2.51 u/L to 82.50 ± 2.65 u/L. ALT levels in the liver also increased from 33.33 ± 2.52 u/L to 61.33 ± 3.21 u/L. These findings confirmed that produced water impairs liver functions and cause significant alterations, thus resulting to fish kills and extinction and must be controlled.

Keywords: Enzymes, Clarias, Produced-Water, Sublethal, Liver.

INTRODUCTION

Produced water is a cocktail of dissolved and dispersed hydrocarbons, heavy metals (such as lead, cadmium, mercury, and arsenic), production chemicals, radionuclides, and high levels of salts. These constituents vary in composition and concentration depending on the geological formation, production methods, and age of the reservoir (Igwo-Ezikpe *et al.*, 2010). In many oil-producing countries, especially developing nations like Nigeria, the management of produced water has remained inadequate due to weak enforcement of environmental regulations, limited technology for water treatment, and poor infrastructure. Consequently, produced water is often discharged untreated or partially treated into rivers, creeks, or onto land surfaces, thereby causing widespread ecological disturbances. As a result of these devastations, there have been agitations for environmental protection and resource control by the affected populace (Ozgun *et al.*, 2013)

Aquatic ecosystems are particularly vulnerable to such discharges. Fish and other aquatic organisms are exposed to toxicants via waterborne routes, either through direct contact, ingestion, or absorption through gills. Studies have shown that chronic exposure to produced water can lead to reduced growth, reproductive failure, tissue damage, and mortality in aquatic organisms (Neff *et al.*, 2011). In Nigeria, the African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) is not only economically important due to its role in aquaculture but also ecologically significant due to its widespread distribution and sensitivity to environmental changes. Its ability to bioaccumulate toxins makes it an excellent bio-monitor for assessing the health of aquatic environments.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

A total of 20 African Cat Fish (*Clarias gariepinus*) were used in this present study. Sample fish were obtained from Kester Fish Farm at Ogboloma Town, Gbarain Kingdom, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State of Nigeria and were transported individually in four plastic jerricans to the Laboratory, Department of Biological Sciences, Niger Delta University, while the Produced Water was collected in a clean container from a Rig site at Imiringi Community, Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa state, Nigeria.

After acclimatization for 14 days, following the method described by Inyang, (2008), three concentrations (30 ml, 40 ml and 50ml) were prepared following the trial test and was used for the main experimental run. The main experimental test lasted for 30 days, following a randomized renewal bioassay. During this period, experimental fishes were randomly selected and exposed to three sub-lethal concentrations of the toxicants obtained from the trial test. The experiment was divided into two groups: one control group with four replicates and three treatment groups with three replicates each.

At the end of the exposure period, a small portion of Liver from experimental fishes were collected by dissection, crushed in a ceramic mortar and homogenized with physiological saline. The mixture was then centrifuged for 15 minutes at 3000 rpm and the supernatant collected in sample bottles for enzymes assay following the method described by Malmstad and Wine-Fordner, (1959).

Statistical Analysis

The data obtained was subjected to analysis using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.8 software and expressed as mean± standard deviation. A one way analysis of Variance was also conducted at $\alpha=0.05$ to determine the significance in the experiment.

RESULT

Table 3.1: Relative activities of Enzyme in the liver of *Clarias gariepinus* exposed to Produce Water for 30 days.

Conc. of PW(mg/L)	ALT (u/L)	AST (u/L)	ACP (u/L)	ALP (u/L)	LDH (u/L)
0.00	41.75±10.21 ^a	7.50±5.80 ^{ab}	21.00±17.94 ^b	22.25±6.24 ^{ab}	34.25±22.34 ^a
0.86	39.25±1.71 ^a	7.50±1.29 ^{ab}	24.75±14.75 ^b	18.00±3.65 ^b	31.25±1.71 ^{ab}
1.10	32.00±4.97 ^a	1.25±0.5 ^b	52.00±23.17 ^a	19.25±1.71 ^b	20.75±2.75 ^b
1.40	69.25±1.71 ^b	13.00±0.82 ^a	23.80±30.04 ^b	23.00±5.89 ^{ab}	40.00±0.82 ^a

All data are expressed as mean ± standard deviation using the software programme Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 20.8. Different superscript indicated a significant variation ($p<0.05$) ^a, ^{ab}, ^b, ^c

DISCUSSIONS

The liver enzymes analyzed include aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), and acid phosphatase (ACP). These biomarkers are sensitive indicators of hepatocellular integrity, metabolic stress, and enzymatic leakage due to toxic exposure. AST levels fluctuated considerably across treatments. The control group recorded 110.5±90.14 u/L. At 0.86 mg/L, AST rose to 157.3±39.63 U/L, indicating mild hepatic stress. However, a sharp decline was observed at 1.1 mg/L (21.75±10.24 u/L), suggesting enzyme inhibition or hepatocyte suppression. Notably, a dramatic increase to 282.5±91.53 u/L at 1.4 mg/L implies severe hepatocellular leakage, possibly due to membrane rupture or necrosis, supporting findings by Nwani *et al.* (2010) that AST surges under high toxicant load.

ALT in the control group was 33.5±29.47 u/L. A significant reduction was observed at 0.86 mg/L (8.00±1.63 u/L), indicative of suppressed transamination activity or mitochondrial interference. Slight recovery was noted at 1.1 mg/L (11.00±2.58 u/L), but still well below control levels. At 1.4 mg/L, ALT remained low (10.25±3.50 u/L), which contrasts with the AST pattern. This disparity may suggest that ALT is less responsive or more inhibited by the constituents of produced water, as also reported by Ayoola (2008). ALP rose significantly at 1.1 mg/L (104.3±21.36 u/L) compared to the control

(89.25±18.30 u/L), suggesting bile duct obstruction or induced synthesis under chemical stress. ALP's moderate reduction at 1.4 mg/L (75.25±7.41 u/L) could reflect adaptive enzyme down regulation. ALP elevation at intermediate concentrations is often associated with cellular repair mechanisms, as observed in other fish studies under petrochemical stress (Adewoye & Fawole, 2012).

LDH, a key enzyme for anaerobic metabolism, was 72.25±54.60 u/L in controls. It dropped sharply at 0.86 mg/L (27.25±6.02 u/L), but recovered slightly at 1.1 and 1.4 mg/L (34.00±3.16 and 32.00±2.45 u/L, respectively). The initial decline might reflect hepatocyte dysfunction or cytosolic enzyme retention, while slight elevations at higher concentrations suggest compensatory metabolic activity due to oxygen stress or hepatic inflammation (Ezeri, 2001). ACP levels in the control group were 332.9±18.25 u/L—markedly higher than all treatment groups. At 0.86 mg/L, ACP dropped drastically to 8.75±2.63 u/L, with gradual recovery at 1.1 mg/L (41.50±21.56 u/L) and 1.4 mg/L (24.50±4.93 u/L). ACP suppression at lower concentrations may indicate lysosomal membrane stabilization, while higher doses trigger lysosomal leakage or autolysis due to severe damage, aligning with Ezeri (2001).

The data collectively show that produced water causes dose-dependent alterations in liver enzyme activities of *Clarias gariepinus*. AST was particularly sensitive, showing a biphasic pattern with peak elevation at the highest concentration. The suppression of ALT and ACP at lower doses, and their partial recovery, implies varying enzyme sensitivity and adaptive physiological responses. These findings reinforce the hepatotoxic nature of produced water and underscore the importance of enzyme biomarkers in aquatic toxicology.

CONCLUSION

After the intoxication period, the find of this research indicates that there was alterations in the values of enzymes compared to the control. This simply is a reflection of hepatocyte dysfunction or cytosolic enzyme retention. The observed slight elevations of enzymes at higher concentrations suggest compensatory metabolic activity due to oxygen stress or hepatic inflammation. It also further indicate enzymatic effect in test exposed sample fishes. The elevation in the values of alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST) also possibly reflect hepatic stress or damage, thus suggesting cellular leakage and compromised liver integrity.

The results thus far suggests that produced water exerts toxicological impact, regardless of the organism's habitat, highlighting potential ecological risks posed by the improper disposal or discharge of produced water into the aquatic environments. The researcher therefore advocate improved waste management practices and reinforcing environmental protection policies to mitigate the detrimental effects of oil industry effluents.

Ethical Issues

The authors are aware of ethical issues as stipulated by the laws of the land and thus completely complied with best practices while carrying out this research.

Competing Interest

Authors declare that there is no conflict of interest that would affect the authenticity and originality of this scientific manuscript.

Authors Contribution

All authors of this research made equal imputes both for data collection, analysis and manuscript writing.

REFERENCES

- Abdel-Moneim, A. M., & El-Murr, A. E. (2015). Biochemical and histopathological effects of industrial wastewater on the liver and kidney of *Clarias gariepinus*. *Environmental Toxicology and Pharmacology*, 39(1), 115–122.
- Abolaji, A. O., Etuk, E. O., & Ibrahim, R. B. (2020). Muscle enzyme alterations in mammals exposed to hydrocarbon contaminants. *Environmental Toxicology and Pharmacology*, 79, 103388.

- Adakole, J. A., & Abolude, D. S. (2012). Haematological changes in the blood of *Clarias gariepinus* exposed to mixture of petroleum products. *Journal of Fisheries International*, 7(3), 55–60.
- Adams, S. M., Ham, K. D., Greeley Jr, M. S., LeHew, R. F., Hinton, D. E., & Saylor, C. F. (2003). Downstream gradients in bioindicator responses: Point source contaminant effects on fish health. *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 59(3), 571–582. <https://doi.org/10.1139/f02-208>
- Adebayo, I. A., Fapohunda, S. O., & Ajani, E. K. (2012). Histopathological changes in the intestine and liver of African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) exposed to sublethal concentrations of tobacco leaf dust. *International Journal of Fisheries and Aquaculture*, 4(3), 45–52.
- Adenkola, A. Y., & Ayo, J. O. (2010). Physiological and biochemical effects of road transportation stress in livestock: A review. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 9(44), 6601–6613.
- Adeogun, A. O., Chukwuka, A. V., & Arukwe, A. (2015). Integrated biomarker responses in *Clarias gariepinus* exposed to effluents from a wastewater treatment plant. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 115, 8–15.
- Adeogun, A. O., Chukwuka, A. V., & Arukwe, A. (2016). Altered immune parameters and histopathological effects in *Clarias gariepinus* exposed to an oilfield-produced water. *Aquatic Toxicology*, 176, 64–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquatox.2016.04.004>
- Adewoye, S. O. (2010). Effects of soap and detergent effluents on the haematological parameters of *Clarias gariepinus*. *Science Focus*, 15(2), 87–93.
- Adewoye, S. O., & Fawole, O. O. (2012). Biochemical response of African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) to effluent from a soap factory. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 11(45), 10322–10329.
- Adewoye, S. O., Fawole, O. O., Owolabi, O. D., & Omotosho, J. S. (2010). Toxicity of cassava wastewater effluents to *Clarias gariepinus* (Burchell, 1822). *American-Eurasian Journal of Scientific Research*, 5(4), 214–220.
- Adeyemi, R. O., Adedapo, A. A., & Oyedapo, O. O. (2016). Toxicological effects of pollutants on serum electrolytes. *Nigerian Journal of Physiological Sciences*, 31(1), 73–78.
- Adeyemi, R. O., Adedeji, O. B., & Famakinde, D. O. (2018). Hematological and biochemical indices of *Clarias gariepinus* exposed to petroleum effluent. *Journal of Environmental Science and Health, Part A*, 53(3), 264–270.
- Adeyemi, R. O., Azeez, M. A., & Adebayo, T. A. (2009). Effects of crude oil contaminated water on *Clarias gariepinus*. *African Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 3(4), 96–101.
- Ehirim, C. N., & Nwankwo, C. N. (2010). Environmental impact of produced water discharges from petroleum exploration and production operations. *Journal of Applied Sciences and Environmental Management*, 14(2), 5–10
- Ezejiolor, A. N., Orisakwe, O. E., & Igwilo, I. O. (2022). Hepatic enzyme disruption in rabbits exposed to petroleum effluent. *Nigerian Journal of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology*, 37(1), 21–28.
- Ezeri, G. N. O. (2001). Hematological response of *Clarias gariepinus* to bacterial infection and environmental stress. *Journal of Aquatic Sciences*, 16(1), 22–24.
- Igwe, J. C., & Abia, A. A. (2006). A bioseparation process for removing heavy metals from waste water using biosorbents. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 5(12), 1167–1179.
- Igwo-Ezikpe, M. N., Otitolaju, A. A., & Chukwu, L. O. (2010). Comparative toxicity of drilling fluids on marine invertebrates (*Perinereis cultrifera* and *Palaemonetes africanus*). *Scientific Research and Essays*, 5(24), 3940–3950.
- Khatib, Z., & Verbeek, P. (2003). Produced water re-injection. *Oilfield Review*, 15(1), 30–41.
- Malmstadt, H.V., & Winefordner, J.D. (1959). Determination of Chloride in Blood serum, Plasma or other Biological Fluids by a New Rapid Precision Method. *Anal. Chem. Acta*, 20, 2-83
- Nduka, J. K., & Orisakwe, O. E. (2011). Water quality issues in the Niger Delta of Nigeria: A look at heavy metal levels and implications. *African Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 5(10), 846–853. <https://doi.org/10.5897/AJEST11.201>

- Neff, J. M., Lee, K., & DeBlois, E. M. (2011). Produced water: Overview of composition, fates, and effects. In K. Lee & J. Neff (Eds.), *Produced water: Environmental risks and advances in mitigation technologies* (pp. 3–54). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-0046-21>
- Nwani, C. D., Aghoghovwia, O. A., & Nwani, S. C. (2010). Acute toxicity of a glyphosate herbicide to African catfish, *Clarias gariepinus*. *Current Research Journal of Biological Sciences*, 2(3), 160–163.
- Nwankwoala, H. O. (2015). The impact of oil and gas activities on groundwater resources in the Niger Delta. *Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 8(4), 174–182.
- Obiezue, R. N., Ezeokonkwo, R. C., & Njoku, C. J. (2020). Muscle electrolytes as biomarkers of environmental stress in mammals. *Nigerian Journal of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology*, 35(1), 89–95.
- Ololade, I. A., & Lajide, L. (2010). Organic geochemical characterization and source identification of contamination in water and sediments of the Niger Delta, Nigeria. *Journal of Environmental Chemistry and Ecotoxicology*, 2(5), 82–90.
- Orem, W. H., Tatu, C. A., Varonka, M., Lerch, H. E., Bates, A. L., Engle, M., & Crosby, L. (2007). Organic substances in produced and formation water from unconventional natural gas extraction in coal and shale. *Applied Geochemistry*, 22(2), 361–368.
- Otokunefor, T. V., & Obiukwu, C. (2019). Assessment of produced water discharge on physiological parameters in terrestrial animals. *Toxicological Reports*, 6, 1203–1210.